

Carbon food labels have limited effects on grocery shopping behavior: Evidence from a randomized field experiment

Abstract

Demand-side food policies are increasingly recognized as important tools for aligning consumption patterns with climate change mitigation targets, and carbon food labels have attracted growing attention as a potential policy instrument. However, evidence on their effectiveness remains mixed, and causal evaluation results from assessing the effects of carbon food labels in real-world supermarket settings is scarce. This study presents evidence from pre-registered randomized experiments combining a representative survey experiment with 2,372 Swiss residents and a large-scale field experiment covering more than five million daily food purchase decisions made by 1,601 consumers over several years. In collaboration with one of Switzerland's largest grocery retailers, we evaluate the causal impact of providing information to increase awareness of one of the world's first carbon food labels implemented in grocery stores on both stated preferences and revealed purchasing behavior. The survey experiment shows that the information treatment significantly increases label awareness and leads to small but positive effects on attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and intentions to consider the climate compatibility of food purchases. In the field experiment, the treatment also affects revealed behavior, but effects are modest and heterogeneous across food categories. Rather than inducing broad shifts away from meat consumption, the label primarily influences within-category choices, including a small decrease in the average emissions of purchased meat products, a higher overall share of labeled products purchased, increased purchases of labeled convenience products, and a partial reallocation within meat consumption (e.g., lower beef and higher pork purchases). We find no evidence of substantial reductions in overall meat purchases or large cross-category substitutions toward plant-based foods. While heavy meat eaters do not react negatively to the treatment, men and more right-wing individuals show a modest behavioral backlash. Overall, the results suggest that carbon food labels capacity to substantially alter habitual food consumption patterns in stimulus-intensive retail environments is limited and should be thus complemented by additional demand-side measures.

Keywords

Food-related emissions, carbon food label, food consumption behavior, plant-based diets, demand-side policy change, field experiment

1. Introduction

A growing body of literature identifies food consumption patterns, especially those of affluent populations, as a key barrier to and important lever for climate change mitigation efforts (Creutzig et al., 2016; IPCC, 2022; Mundaca et al., 2019; Poore & Nemecek, 2018). Shifting diets toward more plant-based, planetary health-aligned consumption patterns could substantially reduce diet-related greenhouse gas emissions, land and water use, biodiversity loss, and diet-related health risks, thereby enhancing long-term global food security (Clark et al., 2020; Crippa et al., 2021; Davies, 2020; IPCC, 2022; Scarborough et al., 2023; Willett et al., 2019). However, food consumption patterns are shaped by deeply ingrained habits influenced by cultural norms, traditions, learned behaviors, values, and social environments (Constantino et al., 2022; Hartmann & Siegrist, 2020; Kukowski et al., 2023) and are therefore difficult to change. In addition, several studies have highlighted a low awareness due to the lack of information and knowledge among the population about the impact of individual food choices as a significant barrier (Camilleri et al., 2019; Hartmann et al., 2021; Taufique et al., 2022). Consequently, demand-side policies aimed at shifting consumption patterns are widely regarded as essential for achieving net zero targets (Aschemann-Witzel & Janssen, 2022; IPCC, 2022; Mundaca et al., 2019; Poore & Nemecek, 2018). This assessment is reinforced by the latest IPCC (2022) report, which clearly highlights the key role of demand-side mitigation solutions in the food sector.

Demand-side food policies encompass a wide spectrum of instruments, ranging from relatively non-intrusive information-based and behavioral instruments (e.g., labels or choice architecture measures such as repositioning plant-based options on menus) to more intrusive market-based instruments (e.g., taxes and subsidies) and regulatory instruments (e.g., minimum requirements for plant-based offerings in public cafeterias) (Ammann et al., 2023). Previous research has examined both the effectiveness and political feasibility of these instruments, suggesting that less intrusive, information-based policies tend to be more publicly acceptable and politically feasible than more intrusive market-based or regulatory policies (Fesenfeld et al., 2020).

One demand-side policy that has increasingly been discussed as a feasible entry-level measure to influence consumer behavior is carbon food labeling, which provides information on the greenhouse gas emissions associated with food products (Camilleri et al., 2019; Lemken et al., 2021; Maier, 2024; Majer et al., 2022; Taufique et al., 2022; Vandenberg et al., 2011). The introduction of such labels is under discussion in the EU, and several private labeling initiatives by companies and/or NGOs have been launched (Kanay et al., 2021; Lemken et al., 2021; Taufique et al., 2022). Existing, mostly survey-based, analyses of the effectiveness of carbon food labels, however, have yielded conflicting results. On the one hand, recent studies show that well-designed labels can increase individuals' general awareness of and knowledge about diet-related emissions (Hartmann et al., 2021; Majer et al., 2022; Panzone et al., 2020), change individuals' stated consumption intentions (Camilleri et al., 2019; Maier, 2024; Meyerding et al., 2019), and even influence revealed consumption behavior (Brunner et al., 2018; Casati et al., 2023; Lohmann et al., 2022) over time. Moreover, such labels have been reported to be positively perceived by consumers (Kramer & Sucky, 2021; Maier, 2024; Pechey et al., 2022), making them a feasible policy measure.

On the other hand, according to the literature the salience of food labels in the purchasing decision and their impact on consumption behavior is limited by label design and visibility issues, information overload and decision context, and factors such as a lack of consumer motivation and ingrained food consumption habits (Camilleri et al., 2019; Edenbrandt et al., 2021; Kanay et al., 2021; Lemken et al., 2021; Panzone et al., 2020; Rondoni & Grasso, 2021). Importantly, only a small number of randomized field experiments have causally evaluated the effects of real-world carbon food labels on revealed regular food consumption behavior. In particular, there is a lack of evidence from randomized field experiments examining the effect of labels on daily grocery shopping behavior in supermarket settings. Existing research has primarily focused on the impact of carbon food labels on hypothetical consumption decisions presented in surveys (Camilleri et al., 2019; Faccioli et al., 2022; Meyerding et al., 2019; Potter et al., 2024; Rondoni & Grasso, 2021) and in living lab settings (Panzone et al., 2024), as well as on individual food consumption decisions when eating out (e.g., in restaurants (Casati et al., 2023) and cafeteria settings (Brunner et al., 2018; Lohmann et al., 2022; Spaargaren et al., 2013).

The present study addresses this gap by conducting a pre-registered large-scale randomized survey and field experiment (Author, 2022) to examine whether information designed to increase awareness of one of the world's first carbon food labels implemented in grocery stores affects consumer behavior. By combining high internal validity with strong external validity, the study enables a causal assessment of how information about a real-world carbon food label in a retail setting influences both stated preferences and revealed purchasing behavior over time. Specifically, the study examines whether providing information to increase awareness of an existing carbon food label is sufficient to change both stated preferences and everyday grocery purchasing behavior. In the survey-experimental component, we investigate how an information treatment about Migros' newly introduced Mcheck label, closely aligned with the information provided in the retailer's real-world communication, affects individuals' attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and behavioral intentions (i.e., stated preferences). In the field-experimental component, we causally evaluate the impact of receiving this information on individuals' revealed food purchasing behavior over time, as observed in transaction-level data.

2. Background

Carbon food labels, as one type of sustainability labels, are intended to increase individuals awareness of diet-related greenhouse gas emissions (Lemken et al., 2021) and, ideally, to facilitate more climate-friendly purchasing decisions by enabling comparisons of food-related carbon emissions both within and across food categories (Garnett, 2023). As highlighted in the Introduction, such labels can be classified as feasible entry-level demand-side policy measures because they rely on voluntary changes in purchasing behavior through information provision, rather than restricting choice sets or imposing financial costs.

Existing evidence on the effectiveness of food labels in shifting consumer behavior varies substantially across contexts and study designs. The literature identifies three key factors that shape the salience and effectiveness of labels in consumption decisions: label awareness, the decision environment, and label design. First, for a label to influence behavior, individuals must be aware of its existence, which often requires accompanying information campaigns or promotional activities (Kaczorowska et al., 2019; Lemken et al., 2021; Majer et al., 2022). Second, the decision environment, namely the context in which purchasing decisions are made, affects whether labels are a salient purchasing criterion and can meaningfully influence behavior. In particular, the number of available choice options and label visibility at the point of purchase are critical for label effectiveness (Buratto & Lotti, 2023; Lemken et al., 2021). Third, label effectiveness depends on design characteristics, with prior studies emphasizing that labels should be easy to understand and concise (Kramer & Sucky, 2021; Lemken et al., 2021). Beyond these design features, labels also need to be perceived as transparent and credible in order to gain consumer trust and affect purchasing decisions (Kramer & Sucky, 2021).

These insights notwithstanding, most existing evidence on the effectiveness of labels is based on survey experiments or controlled settings, leaving open the question of whether carbon food labels affect revealed consumption behavior in real-world grocery retail environments. This gap is particularly relevant given that supermarkets are stimulus-intensive decision environments characterized by high information density, multiple competing labels, price signals, and other visual stimuli. Furthermore, in this context there is a tendency for information overload, amongst others due to many different labels and thus overall label awareness, especially for more newly introduced labels, tends to be low (Kramer & Sucky, 2021). As a result, findings from hypothetical or controlled contexts may not generalize to real-world shopping situations, underscoring the need for causal field experiments conducted in retail settings.

In the present study, building on the literature on the intention-behavior gap (Aschemann-Witzel & Zielke, 2017; Sheeran & Webb, 2016; Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Berndsen & Pligt, 2004; Eker et al., 2019; Fishbein, 2008; Lacroix & Gifford, 2020; Sussman & Gifford, 2019), we expect that providing information about a relatively new carbon food label to increase label awareness will positively affect individuals' attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and intentions to reduce diet-related emissions (i.e., stated preferences). We also expect that increasing awareness of the label will have a positive effect on individuals' revealed shopping behavior. However, given generally low label awareness (Kramer & Sucky, 2021), particularly for newly introduced labels, the stimulus-intensive supermarket environment, and the strongly habitual nature of food consumption (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2020), we expect these effects on revealed purchasing behavior to be modest. In other words, the intention-behavior gap is likely to remain substantial.

Empirically, we test these pre-registered expectations (Fesenfeld & Maier, 2022) using both a survey experiment ($N = 2,372$) and a field experiment ($N = 1,601$) conducted with a representative sample of Swiss residents in cooperation with the Swiss retailer Migros. Migros introduced one of the world's first large-scale carbon food labels in 2021. The so-called Mcheck label (see Fig. 1) assigns food products a rating on a five-point ordinal star scale, ranging from one star (worst climate footprint) to five stars (best climate footprint). Only whole-star ratings are used.

Figure 1 – Example of the Mcheck label on Migros food products in Switzerland. (Migros, 2022) The label text reads “climate compatibility” and is displayed in Switzerland’s three official languages (German, French, and Italian), as is standard practice for food product labels. More information on the label can be found in Appendix E.

The Mcheck climate food label, developed and verified in collaboration with external scientific partners (Migros, 2022), ranks food products based on their absolute carbon emissions from production, packaging, and transport. Emission values are derived from internationally recognized databases. For many products, Migros – working with the life cycle assessment (LCA) company intep – assigns category-level emissions values (e.g., identical values for all apples). For high-impact categories such as meat, product-specific LCAs are conducted that account for sourcing and production methods. Although only the star rating is displayed on product packaging (not specific emission values), this approach allows for variation in climate ratings even within product categories. Importantly, the one-to-five-star ratings are based on an absolute emissions scale rather than relative comparisons within categories, enabling cross-category climate impact comparisons. The Mcheck label has been gradually introduced since March 2021 on Migros’ own brands, which account for approximately 80 percent of its food product range. The label is not displayed on fresh products, such as unpackaged fruit and vegetables, and currently about 25 percent of all food products carry the Mcheck climate label. Despite this relatively broad rollout, Table 1 shows that familiarity with the Mcheck label among survey participants was low prior to the experiment.

		Low familiarity		Medium familiarity	High familiarity		
Prior Mcheck awareness	Not at all familiar	Not familiar	Rather not familiar	Neither nor	Rather familiar	Familiar	Very familiar
Share of participants	9%	14%	20%	15%	19%	17%	6%

Table 1 – Overview of Mcheck familiarity among 2372 survey participants measured in the survey with the matrix question item “Are you at this moment not at all or very familiar with the following food labels?” listing, amongst others, the Mcheck label measuring familiarity with a 7-point Likert scale from 1 = Not at all familiar to 7= Very familiar (also see Appendix B1).

Given Migros’ large market share of approximately 35 percent in Switzerland (Statista, 2020), the novelty of the label, and the low baseline level of consumer awareness, the Mcheck initiative provides a particularly suitable case for examining whether increasing awareness of a widely available yet relatively new and unfamiliar carbon food label can translate into changes in consumer behavior in a real-world grocery shopping context. By combining an information intervention closely aligned with Migros’ real-world communication with both survey-based and behavioral outcomes, the study allows us to assess whether increased label awareness affects individuals’ attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and behavioral intentions, and whether such changes extend to revealed purchasing behavior over time. Given the substantial share of participants who were initially unfamiliar with the Mcheck label (Table 1), the information treatment primarily increased label awareness and potentially salience, functioning as a first meaningful encounter for less familiar participants and as a reinforcement for those already aware of the label.

Methods

In the first, *survey-experimental part* of the study, we conducted a quantitative survey experiment between May and June 2022. Respondents were randomly assigned to either a control group, which received no additional information, or a treatment group, which was exposed to information about the Mcheck label (see the Survey Procedure and Measures section below for details on the treatment design). The information treatment was designed to closely mirror Migros' real-world communication about the label, as used in its advertising and online information materials, thereby enhancing the ecological validity of the experimental manipulation.

In the second, *field experimental part*, we analyzed revealed purchasing behavior using anonymized transaction data from participants who provided informed consent to link their survey responses to their purchasing records. These data were made available by Migros via its Cumulus customer database (see the Study Sample section for further details). The transaction data cover all grocery purchases made by consenting participants from March 1, 2020, until approximately twelve months after the conclusion of the survey experiment (i.e., through May 2023). This extended observation window allows us to examine both short- and longer-term effects of the information treatment on individuals' real-world food purchasing behavior.

2.1 Sample

Approval from the University of Bern ethics committee was obtained prior to data collection for both parts of the study. The survey instrument was pretested with a convenience sample of 20 students to assess clarity, timing, and comprehension. Subsequently, participants were recruited via an online panel administered by a commercial sampling provider (Kantar Group, Munich, Germany). Respondents were informed that they were taking part in a study on food consumption and product preferences and received a small financial incentive for participation. Quota sampling was applied using interlocked quotas on gender and age, as well as a quota on canton of residence, to approximate the demographic distribution of the Swiss population (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021). Details on screening criteria are provided in Appendix A. Participation in the survey was restricted to individuals who were members of Migros' Cumulus customer loyalty program, as the Cumulus database was used to retrieve anonymized transaction data for participants who consented to the field-experimental component of the study. Importantly, consent to share purchasing data was not required for participation in the survey experiment and therefore did not constitute an exclusion criterion at the recruitment stage. To minimize item non-response, the survey employed forced-choice questions throughout. The final survey-experimental sample consisted of $N = 2,372$ respondents. Of these, $N = 1,601$ participants (67.5%) provided informed consent to link their survey responses to anonymized purchasing data, forming the sample for the field-experimental analysis of revealed purchasing behavior. The demographic and structural composition of the full survey sample and the field-experimental subsample did not differ significantly. Both samples closely resembled the Swiss residential population in the German- and French-speaking regions with respect to gender and age. However, compared to the general population, respondents were on average more highly educated, reported somewhat lower household income, and self-identified as slightly more left-leaning politically. A detailed comparison between the sample and population benchmarks is provided in Appendix B1 (Table 2).

2.2 Survey Procedure and Measures

Qualtrics (an online survey software application) was used to design and administer the survey experiment for the first part of the study. The median survey completion time was approximately 22 minutes. Participants could complete the survey in either German or French, depending on their language preference. They were informed that the study concerned food consumption and food product preferences. Following eligibility screening and an initial block of demographic questions, respondents answered a series of items measuring control variables identified in the food consumption literature as key predictors of food purchasing behavior and attention to sustainability attributes, including the climate compatibility of diets. To avoid priming effects, the focus on the Mcheck label was intentionally disguised. In particular, the Mcheck familiarity item was embedded within a broader, neutral battery assessing familiarity with multiple food labels commonly used in Swiss supermarkets, which was presented prior to the experimental treatment (see full questionnaire in Appendix D).

The control items included questions on: a) the respondent's diet, since current meat consumption habits have a particularly significant impact on the CO₂ footprint of diets (IPES-Food, 2022; Swiss National Science Foundation, 2020; Willett et al., 2019); b) their sustainable food shopping criteria (ssc) to see how much emphasis they put on sustainability criteria such as the environmental and climate impacts of food products (Fesenfeld et al., 2020, 2021); c) their label opinion to measure their general perception of food labels; d) their awareness of various food labels used in Swiss supermarkets, including the Mcheck label, to indicate prior Mcheck awareness (Kramer & Sucky, 2021); e) their use of a shopping list as a proxy for translating purchasing intentions into actual behavior (Kamm et al., 2015); f) their food shopping behavior, i.e., their frequency of

(personally) going food shopping, as a predictor of stronger or weaker involvement in food purchasing (Apostolidis & McLeay, 2016); g) their frequency of visits to supermarkets, including Migros, to check Migros shopping frequency and thus the potential frequency of exposure to the Mcheck label; and, h) their prior knowledge about the climate impact of food products to help determine their understanding of the impact of food production and consumption on the climate (Hartmann et al., 2021), amongst other factors – see details on variables in Appendix B1 – Table 2 and the detailed question wording in the questionnaire in Appendix D.

Subsequently, respondents were randomly assigned to either a control group, which received no additional information, or a treatment group. The treatment consisted of exposure to realistic information about the Mcheck label, closely based on information provided on the Migros website, followed by an illustrative example of label use. In the introductory part of the treatment, participants were informed that they would see an excerpt from the information campaign accompanying Migros' Mcheck label. While Fig. 2 displays the German version of this first part of the treatment (see English translation in the figure caption), the text was presented to the respondents in the respective survey language selected (German or French).

Figure 2 - Information treatment part I. Information shown to participants in the treatment group. Participants were informed that the displayed text was an excerpt from the information campaign accompanying Migros' M-Check label. The original text was presented in German or French, depending on the survey language chosen. English translation of the text on top: "Simple sustainable shopping: With the Mcheck, we want to make sustainable shopping easier for you. We closely examine our own brands and have them evaluated by external experts with regard to animal welfare and climate compatibility, using a five-star rating system. With the Mcheck on the packaging, you can immediately see how sustainable our products are.". English translation of the text in the green part below: "Mcheck: See at a glance how sustainable the product is."

In the second part of the treatment, participants were shown an example demonstrating how the Mcheck label can be used to compare products across food categories (Fig. 3). The example contrasts conventional meat products (chicken, beef, and pork) with a plant-based meat substitute to highlight differences in climate compatibility ratings. Although the Mcheck label covers multiple sustainability dimensions, including animal welfare, the analysis focuses exclusively on the climate compatibility dimension. This choice reflects data constraints: at the time of the study, animal welfare ratings were available for only a very limited set of products and exhibited very little variation, which would have resulted in collinearity and imprecise estimates.

Accordingly, in the example, the animal welfare rating was held constant across meat products, while no animal welfare label was displayed for the meat substitute product, which contains no animal-based ingredients. To support participants' understanding of the climate metric, the example replicated the presentation used in the Migros online shop, where CO₂ emission ranges underlying the Mcheck ratings are illustrated using car travel equivalents. Identical product images were used across all four items to isolate the informational effect of the label itself while holding visual product characteristics constant. The example was designed to highlight two key features of the Mcheck label: (1) the higher climate compatibility of plant-based alternatives relative to conventional meat, and (2) the label's ability to facilitate cross-category comparisons of climate impacts.

Figure 3 - Information treatment part II. The figure compares conventional meat products (chicken, beef, and pork) with a plant-based meat substitute in terms of CO₂ emissions and Mcheck climate ratings. The animal welfare rating is held constant across meat products, and no animal welfare label is shown for the plant-based product. In line with the standard presentation in the Migros online shop, the CO₂ emission ranges underlying the Mcheck ratings are illustrated using car travel equivalents to facilitate interpretation. The figure was displayed in German or French depending on the selected survey language (English translation shown). See Appendix E for further details on the Mcheck label.

After exposure to the treatment, respondents completed a set of dependent variable measures using seven-point Likert scales. These included attitudes toward paying attention to climate compatibility when food shopping, perceived behavioral control, and behavioral intentions related to reducing the carbon footprint of their diets (see Appendix B1, Table 1). Perceived behavioral control was measured using two items capturing perceived ease and self-efficacy of paying attention to climate compatibility during food shopping (Sussman & Gifford, 2019).

Finally, a manipulation check assessed respondents' updated awareness of the Mcheck label, attitudes toward private labeling initiatives, perceptions of Migros, and perceived effectiveness and credibility of private labels. The survey concluded with questions on political ideology, political position, and party support, followed by a second block of demographic questions (e.g., income and household size).

2.3 Purchasing data procedure and measures

In collaboration with Migros and as part of the independent evaluation of the Mcheck climate label, Migros provided anonymized transaction-level purchasing data for the subset of survey participants who gave informed consent to data linkage (N = 1,601). The dataset covers the period from March 2020 to May 2023 and comprises more than five million individual purchase observations at the product level.

To prepare the raw transaction data for analysis, purchased food products were first classified into four analytically relevant food categories that constitute the focus of this study: meat products, meat substitutes, vegetarian convenience products, and fruit, vegetables, and legumes. While the raw dataset contains additional food categories, these categories are not examined in the present analysis. To limit the influence of extreme purchase quantities, outliers were identified separately for each food category based on the distribution of positive purchase amounts. Specifically, within each category, observations below the 1st percentile or above the 99th percentile of the category-specific distribution were classified as outliers and excluded prior to aggregation and regression analyses. This category-specific trimming approach preserves meaningful within-category variation while reducing the influence of implausibly small or large purchase quantities that could disproportionately affect the results. Following outlier removal, all purchases within the relevant categories were aggregated at the individual-by-day level, yielding a customer × shopping-day unbalanced panel structure. This aggregation reflects daily grocery shopping behavior and corresponds to the temporal unit at which individuals are likely to be exposed to the Mcheck label in real-world retail settings. The panel is unbalanced because individuals shop at Migros with varying frequency over time, resulting in differing numbers of observed shopping days per participant. For more fine-grained analyses, meat products were further disaggregated along two dimensions. First, all meat products were subdivided into meat products (including

fresh and processed items such as plain or seasoned meat, cold cuts, and sausages) and meat convenience products (e.g., pizza, ready meals, and sandwiches). Second, all meat products were classified by meat type, distinguishing poultry, pork, beef, and other meats. To capture different dimensions of purchasing behavior, the dependent variables summarized in Table 2 were used for the analysis.

Outcome group	Outcome variables	Description	Transformation / scale	
Mcheck climate rating outcomes	DV1	Mcheck climate mean (all products)	Average Mcheck climate rating of all purchased products per shopping day	Standardized (z-score), daily mean
	DV1a-DV1e	Mcheck climate mean by food type	Average Mcheck climate rating of purchased products within specific food categories (all meat products, meat convenience products, meat substitutes, fruit, vegetables and legumes, vegetarian convenience products) calculated per shopping day	Standardized (z-score), daily mean
	DV1f	Mcheck climate share	Proportion of purchased products carrying an Mcheck label per shopping day	Proportion (0–1)
Purchased amounts	DV2–DV6	Amount by food category	Total amount (in grams) of all meat products, meat convenience products, meat substitutes, fruit, vegetables and legumes, and vegetarian convenience products purchased per shopping day	$\log(1 + x)$
	DV7–DV10	Amount by meat type	Total amount (in grams) of poultry, pork, beef, and other meat products purchased per shopping day	$\log(1 + x)$
Label uptake within and across food categories	DV2a–DV6a	Share of labeled products across categories	Proportion of purchased products with an Mcheck label within each food category relative to the total number of Mcheck–labeled products purchased per shopping day	Proportion (0–1)
	DV7a–DV10a	Share of labeled products across meat types	Proportion of purchased products with an Mcheck label within each meat category relative to the total number of Mcheck–labeled products purchased per shopping day	Proportion (0–1)
	DV2b–DV6b	Within-category label share	Proportion of Mcheck–labeled products within each food category relative to all products purchased in that category per shopping day	Proportion (0–1)
	DV7b–DV10b	Within-meat-type label share	Proportion of Mcheck–labeled products within each meat category relative to all products purchased in that category per shopping day	Proportion (0–1)

Table 2 - Overview of dependent variables derived from purchasing data. Note that purchased amount variables exhibit strong right-skewness and include a substantial number of zero observations (i.e., shopping days without purchases in a specific category). To address these distributional properties, all amount-based dependent variables were transformed using the $\log(1 + y)$ transformation prior to estimation. This transformation reduces skewness and retains zero-purchase observations.

Together, these measures allow us to examine not only changes in overall purchasing quantities but also shifts in the climate rating of purchased products and the relative uptake of Mcheck–labeled items across food categories and meat types. See more details on the dependent variables in Appendix C1 – Table 9.

2.4 Survey data analysis

Balance checks confirm that random assignment to the treatment was successful: the treatment and control groups do not differ statistically across a wide range of socio-demographic, economic, political, and diet-related characteristics (see Appendix A4). This indicates that any observed differences in outcomes can be causally attributed to the information treatment. To increase statistical efficiency and robustness, the survey-experimental analyses include a set of pre-specified socio-demographic, political, and behavioral control variables that have been shown in prior research to be associated with food consumption, purchasing behavior, and policy preference (Stock & Watson, 2020; see Appendix B1 - Table 2). Including these covariates improves precision without affecting the consistency of the treatment effect estimates due to random assignment. For each survey-based dependent variable, we estimated linear regression models with robust standard errors:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{Group}_i + X_i' \beta + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where Y_i denotes the dependent variable of interest for individual i , Group_i is a binary indicator equal to one for respondents assigned to the treatment group (with the control group as the reference category), Maier et al. 2025 Substitute experiment survey data paper These include age, gender, education, perceptions of food labels, and other characteristics shown to be relevant for food consumption, purchasing behavior, and policy support (see Appendix B1). The error term ε_i captures unobserved factors affecting the outcome.

Because multiple outcome variables were analyzed, we adjusted p-values to account for multiple hypothesis testing using the Benjamini–Hochberg (1995) procedure to control the false discovery rate. Reported significance levels therefore refer to adjusted p-values unless stated otherwise.

2.5 Purchasing data analysis

According to our balance checks, the randomization of the treatment in the sub-sample of respondents agreeing to anonymously share their consumption data also successfully led to the treatment and control groups being not statistically different across various socio-demographic, economic and diet-related variables (see Appendix C5). To analyze the impact of the information treatment on food purchasing behavior over time, we estimate panel regression models with individual and time fixed effects. Individual fixed effects control for unobserved factors that are constant within individuals over time (Stock & Watson, 2020), such as stable preferences, habits, or cultural norms. Time fixed effects capture shocks and influences that are common across individuals but vary over time (Stock & Watson, 2020), such as nationwide Mcheck information campaigns. The panel dataset is unbalanced, as individuals differ in their shopping frequency and therefore are not observed on every calendar day. Importantly, the dataset records daily purchase amounts for a predefined set of focal food categories (meat, meat convenience, meat substitutes, and vegetarian convenience products, as well as fruit, vegetables and legumes). Purchase amounts are coded as zero for product categories not purchased on a given shopping day, while days on which individuals do not purchase any of the focal categories are excluded by design. As a result, the data exhibit substantial skewness and a high share of zeros at the category–day level, which is typical for grocery transaction data. For the primary analysis, the following panel regression models with heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation robust standard errors were calculated for each dependent variable:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 * \text{Group_p}_{it} + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + u_{it} \quad (2)$$

In the panel regression models, Y stands for the dependent variable. Group_p is a dummy variable that takes a value of ‘0’ for all participants before participating in the survey, remains ‘0’ for the control group after participating in the study, and takes on a value of ‘1’ for all participants in the treatment group as soon as they participated in the survey. Further, α_i is the individual fixed effect, and λ_t is the time fixed effect.

To account for skewed outcome distributions and the prevalence of zero purchases, all continuous purchase amount variables are analyzed using a $\log(1 + y)$ transformation. This transformation allows the inclusion of zero values while reducing the influence of extreme observations in highly skewed transaction data. To further assess robustness, we estimate two-part models that separately examine (i) the extensive margin, i.e., the probability of purchasing a given category on a shopping day, and (ii) the intensive margin, i.e., the conditional purchase amount given a positive purchase. These analyses clarify whether estimated treatment effects reflect changes in purchase incidence, purchase intensity, or both. In addition, we re-estimate the main models using an alternative $\log(0.1 + y)$ transformation to examine the sensitivity of the results to the choice of constant added prior to logging. This specification reduces the relative influence of near-zero values and provides a conservative check against potential log-scale amplification effects. Given that several regression models were ran, a p-adjustment was performed to control for false discovery due to multiple comparisons using the Benjamini & Hochberg (1995) method. As an additional robustness check, panel models with individual clustered standard errors were calculated. For details on the robustness checks see Appendix C4. For the second part of the analysis, the following panel regression models with heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation robust standard errors were calculated for each dependent variable, controlling for potential interaction effects:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 * \text{Group_p}_{it} + \beta_2 * X_{it} + \beta_3 * (\text{Group_p}_{it} * X_{it}) + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + u_{it} \quad (3)$$

Here, X_{it} represents a set of moderating and control variables, including: a) *prior Mcheck label awareness*, indicating initial familiarity with the Mcheck label before eventually being treated in the survey on a scale from 1 = not at all familiar to 7 = completely familiar; b) *weeks treated*, indicating time (weeks passed) since participating in the survey; c) *diet*, indicating dietary patterns with 1 = vegan/vegetarian, 2 = pescetarian, 3 = flexitarian with meat consumption once a week or less, 4 = high meat consumption with meat several times a week, 5 = heavy meat consumption with meat every day or several times a day; d) *sustainable food shopping criteria index*, summing the specific factors related to sustainable shopping criteria including environmental impact, organic certification, regionality, etc. and dividing the sum by the number of items; e) *taste and safety food shopping criteria index*, summing the specific factors related to taste and safety shopping criteria including taste, safety, health, and nutrition, etc., and dividing the sum by the number of items; f) *price*, indicating the importance of price when food shopping; g) *ease of preparation*, indicating the importance of the ease of preparing a food when food shopping; h) *prior knowledge* on the environmental impact of foods; i) *label opinion index*, summing the specific factors related to label opinions and dividing the sum by the number of items; j) *left-right political self-placement*; k.) *government intervention*, indicating the preference for more or less governmental regulation; as well as important demographic variables such as *age*, *gender*, *education* and *income*. More details on the control and moderating variables can be found in Appendix C1 – Table 10. Please also note that all moderation analyses are exploratory and should be interpreted descriptively, as the moderator variables were not randomly assigned.

3. Results

3.1 Survey results

In the survey experimental part, following our pre-registered expectations, we tested for the effects of the carbon food label information treatment on consumers' stated preferences and attitudinal variables. A total of 2,372 participants were randomly assigned to either the treatment group (N=1,183), which received information on the Mcheck label, or the control group (N=1,189), which did not receive this information (see Methods section and further details in Maier (2024)). Our manipulation checks (see Appendix B5) confirm that the information treatment successfully increased both awareness of the Mcheck label ($p < .001$) and the intention to take it into account when shopping ($p < .001$). The manipulation checks further indicate that participants in the treatment group reported significantly higher perceived credibility ($p < .01$) and effectiveness ($p < .001$) of voluntary labelling initiatives than those in the control group.

Fig. 4 shows the main results of the label information treatment on the selected stated preference and attitudinal variables based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Fishbein, 2008; Sussman & Gifford, 2019), i.e., attitudes towards paying attention to climate compatibility when food shopping, perceived behavioral control (measured through perceived self-efficacy and perceived ease of undertaking a behavior), and intention to reduce diet-related emissions.

Figure 4 - Main effects of the information treatment compared to control group (dashed baseline). Standardized treatment effects on the outcome variables (intention to pay attention to the climate compatibility of foods when shopping, self-efficacy of paying attention to climate compatibility, perceived ease, and attitudes towards carbon food labels) are presented in four colors. All outcome variables are measured on a seven-point Likert scale, with higher values indicating stronger intention to change attitude, personal consumption, etc. (see details in Method section). The error bars represent the 95 percent confidence intervals (outer bar) and the 90 percent confidence intervals (inner thicker bar) based on OLS regressions with robust standard errors. Point markers indicate statistical significance after Benjamini-Hochberg adjustment for multiple testing. The respective regression output tables can be seen in Appendix B2, as well as further details in (Author, 2024)

In line with our pre-registered hypotheses, participants in the treatment group had significantly more positive attitudes ($p_{adj} < .001$) toward paying attention to climate compatibility when shopping for food and increased intentions ($p_{adj} < .05$) to pay attention to their food-related climate impact compared to members of the control group. In addition, the perceived self-efficacy ($p_{adj} < .01$) and ease ($p_{adj} < .001$) of paying attention to food-related climate impacts increased significantly. The results show that the label information treatment positively affects individuals' attitudes, perceived behavioral control (measured by perceived self-efficacy and ease of performing a specific behavior (Sussman & Gifford, 2019)), and behavioral intention to reduce food consumption-

related emissions. Moreover, robustness checks (see Appendix B4) show that the treatment effects remain significant in the subsample of those $N = 1601$ participants who gave their informed consent to have their purchase data anonymously evaluated for the field experimental part of the study. However, for both the full sample and the subsample the effect sizes are small (Lovakov & Agadullina, 2021), ranging from 0.12-0.27 on a 7-point Likert scale. Moreover, importantly we only find very small or nonsignificant differences in treatment effects for participants with or without prior awareness about the Mcheck prior to the start of the experiment (Author, 2024).

3.2 Field experimental results

In the field experimental part of the study, we tested our pre-registered expectations about the effects of the label treatment on consumers' revealed purchasing behavior. For this part of the study, a subset of $N = 1,601$ respondents gave informed consent to allow us to anonymously evaluate their daily food purchase data over time. By obtaining consent *before* randomizing respondents into treatment and control groups, we avoided potential self-selection bias and obtained a balanced sample of $N = 802$ participants in the control group and $N = 799$ in the treatment group. The shopping data used for our panel analysis consists of all daily food purchases made by these respondents at Migros over a period of about three years, i.e., data from about two years before the treatment to about one year after (see details in Methods section).

First, Fig. 5a provides a descriptive overview of the distribution of Mcheck climate ratings among currently labeled products within each food category of interest in our sample of purchased products in the treatment and control group. As expected, average Mcheck ratings (shown in brackets) vary across categories. Categories with predominantly plant-based products exhibit higher average ratings, such as fruit, vegetables, and legumes (mean = 4.7), vegetarian convenience products (mean = 3.7), and meat substitutes (mean = 3.5). In contrast, animal-based categories display lower average ratings, including meat products (mean = 2.4), meat convenience products (mean = 3.1), poultry (mean = 2.6), pork (mean = 1.9), and beef (mean = 1.3). Fig. 5b complements this by showing, for the same food categories, the proportion of purchased products in our sample with versus without an Mcheck label. The share of purchased products carrying an Mcheck label is higher for meat substitutes (36%) and vegetarian convenience products (49%) than for fruit, vegetables and legumes (14%), meat products (11%) and meat convenience products (25%). Notably, within meat categories, labeled poultry products account for a much larger share of purchases (30%) than labeled pork (4%) or beef products (3%).

Figure 5 – Distribution of Mcheck climate ratings and labeling coverage across food categories. Panel (a) shows the proportion of all Mcheck-labeled products purchased that fall into each rating category (1–5) for the different food categories. Panel (b) displays, for each food category (all meat products; poultry, pork, and beef; meat substitutes; fruit, vegetables and legumes; and vegetarian convenience), the share of Mcheck-labeled products relative to all products purchased. Note that the category fruit, vegetables, and legumes with an Mcheck label excludes all fresh fruit and vegetables, as the retailer Migros excludes fresh, non-packaged products from the Mcheck label (see Introduction for more information on the Mcheck label).

In the following, we describe the main results of the panel analysis with time and individual fixed effects that tested the effect of the information treatment on the revealed daily food purchasing behavior (see Appendix C2 for the regression tables).

First, as shown in Fig. 6 and the panel regression results, the information treatment did not significantly affect the overall average Mcheck climate rating of all food products purchased, nor the average Mcheck climate rating of meat convenience products, meat substitute products, fruit, vegetables and legumes, or vegetarian convenience products. However, the treatment significantly increased the average standardized Mcheck climate rating of meat products purchased by approximately 6.7 percentage points ($p < .05$). Although the effect size is small, it provides evidence that the label primarily affected product choice within the meat category, rather than leading to across product shifts, for instance through substitution away from meat products per se. Further, the treatment significantly increased the share of Mcheck-labeled products in total daily food purchases by about 1.1 percentage points ($p_{adj} < .001$) relative to the control group. This small but statistically significant increase indicates heightened awareness of, and attention to, the Mcheck label, suggesting that the information treatment worked as intended.

Figure 6 – Main effects of information treatment compared to control group (dashed baseline). Shown are standardized treatment effects on the average Mcheck climate rating of (a) all purchased products; (b) meat products (including meat convenience); (c) meat convenience products; (d) meat substitutes; (e) fruits, vegetables, and legumes; (f) vegetarian convenience products; and (g) the share of Mcheck-labeled products purchased per shopping trip. Error bars indicate 95% (outer) and 90% (inner) confidence intervals from panel regressions with robust standard errors. Point markers denote statistical significance after Benjamini–Hochberg adjustment. Corresponding regression results are reported in Appendix C2.

Further, as shown in Fig. 7 and the panel regression results, the treatment did not significantly affect the average amount of all meat products purchased (including fresh meat and meat convenience products) relative to the control group. This null effect contrasts with our initial expectation that the climate label would reduce overall meat purchases. Instead, the treatment primarily affected specific subcategories. The treatment group increased purchases of meat convenience products by about 9.1% ($p_{\text{adj}} < .001$), corresponding to a small, standardized effect of approximately 0.04 standard deviations. In absolute terms, this corresponds to an average increase of roughly 9 grams per shopping day relative to the control-group mean (about 103 g). Decomposition into extensive and intensive margins shows that this increase reflects both a higher probability of purchasing meat convenience products and slightly larger conditional purchase amounts (see Appendix C4, Tables 14a-d). Similarly, vegetarian convenience purchases increased by about 8.6% ($p_{\text{adj}} < .001$; 0.03 SD), corresponding to an average increase of approximately 23 grams per shopping day relative to a control-group mean of about 266 g, again driven by changes along both margins. Purchases of meat substitute products increased by about 2.2% ($p_{\text{adj}} < .05$; 0.02 SD) which translates into an average increase of less than half a gram per shopping day (about 0.4 g relative to a baseline of about 19 g). In contrast to convenience products, however, this effect is entirely driven by the extensive margin: the treatment increases the likelihood that consumers purchase meat substitutes at least once, while conditional quantities among buyers remain unchanged. This pattern is consistent with occasional trial or experimentation rather than sustained changes in consumption intensity. Purchases of fruit, vegetables, and legumes did not respond significantly on either margin. One plausible explanation for these patterns is that packaged convenience products are more likely to carry an Mcheck label and are therefore more salient at the point of purchase. Descriptive evidence indeed shows higher shares of labeled products within convenience categories compared to other food categories (see Fig. 3b).

Figure 7 – Main effects of information treatment compared to control group (dashed baseline). Shown are standardized treatment effects on the average amount purchased of (a) all meat products (including fresh meat, sausages, cold cuts, and meat convenience products); (b) meat convenience products (e.g., pizza, ready meals, sandwiches); (c) meat substitutes (products designed to replicate the taste and appearance of meat); (d) fruits, vegetables, and legumes (including both fresh and packaged produce, canned or pickled items, dried fruits, and legumes); and (e) vegetarian convenience products (e.g., pizza, sandwiches, ready meals, tofu, seitan, and falafel). Error bars indicate 95% (outer) and 90% (inner) confidence intervals from panel regressions with robust standard errors. Point markers denote statistical significance after Benjamini–Hochberg adjustment. Corresponding regression results are reported in Appendix C2.

Within meat categories, we observe a partial reallocation rather than a reduction in total meat consumption. As shown in Fig. 8, pork purchases increased by about 5.2% ($p_{\text{adj}} < .05$; 0.01 SD), corresponding to about 16 additional grams per shopping day relative to a control-group mean of about 299 g, primarily driven by a higher

probability of purchase. In contrast, beef purchases declined by about 4.3% ($p_{adj} < .05$; 0.02 SD), equivalent to an average reduction of approximately 4 grams per shopping day relative to a baseline of about 92 g, reflecting both fewer purchase occasions and smaller conditional quantities. Poultry purchases show no consistent pattern. Taken together, these findings suggest substitution within meat consumption away from beef toward pork and convenience-oriented products, rather than a broad shift away from meat.

Figure 8 – Main effects of information treatment compared to control group (dashed baseline). Displayed are standardized treatment effects on the average amount purchased per shopping trip of (c) poultry products, (d) pork products, and (e) beef products (all subcategories of total meat purchases). Error bars indicate 95% (outer) and 90% (inner) confidence intervals from panel regressions with robust standard errors. Point markers denote statistical significance after Benjamini–Hochberg adjustment. Corresponding regression results are reported in Appendix C2.

Given the high day-to-day variability and frequent zero purchases typical of grocery transaction data, percentage changes derived from log specifications can appear sizeable in relative terms. However, standardized effect sizes remain small across outcomes, indicating marginal behavioral adjustments relative to the overall dispersion of daily purchases. To ensure that these results are not driven by zero inflation or log-scale amplification near zero, we conduct several robustness checks (Appendix C4). Two-part models separating extensive and intensive margins confirm that significant effects reflect identifiable changes in purchase incidence and/or conditional quantities rather than mechanical scaling artifacts. Re-estimating the models using an alternative $\log(0.1 + y)$ transformation yields substantively identical results, including the absence of an effect on total meat purchases and the presence of small increases in convenience and substitute categories. Additional robustness checks show no significant treatment effects on the proportion of Mcheck-labeled products within food categories, indicating that quantity effects are not solely driven by compositional changes in label uptake. Overall, these analyses suggest statistically significant but behaviorally modest adjustments in purchasing behavior.

In addition, to examine potential dynamics in treatment effects, we interacted the label information treatment with the number of weeks since treatment exposure. We find evidence of a positive and significant treatment–time interaction for meat convenience purchases, suggesting a gradual build-up of the treatment effect over time. For all other outcome variables, treatment–time interactions are small and statistically insignificant (see Appendix C4, Tables 16 a and b).

Lastly, to explore potential heterogeneity in treatment effects across population subgroups, we conducted exploratory moderation analyses by interacting the label information treatment with a set of individual

characteristics that may condition its impact on purchasing behavior. These included respondents' prior familiarity with the Mcheck label, baseline meat consumption frequency (diet), food purchasing criteria (e.g., sustainability, taste, food safety, and price sensitivity), political ideology (left–right self-placement), and key sociodemographic variables (see Methods section for details). To facilitate comparison across moderators, all interaction variables were standardized (z-transformed). Overall, the exploratory interaction analyses reveal modest but systematic heterogeneity in treatment effects across selected individual characteristics (see Appendix C3). In particular, higher education levels and stronger sustainable food purchasing criteria are associated with more positive responses to the information treatment. For example, among more highly educated respondents, the treatment led to larger increases in the average Mcheck climate rating of purchased products, as well as higher purchases of meat substitutes.

By contrast, political ideology and gender moderate treatment effects in the opposite direction. More right-leaning individuals and men exhibit less favorable responses to the treatment, including relatively higher purchases of meat products and lower purchases of meat substitutes and vegetarian convenience products, consistent with a modest behavioral backlash. Importantly, we do not find evidence that prior familiarity with the Mcheck label significantly moderates treatment effects, suggesting that the information intervention had similar effects among respondents with both low and high baseline awareness. Treatment effects also do not differ substantially by baseline meat consumption levels. Taken together, these findings suggest that heterogeneity in treatment effects is driven less by prior consumption habits and more by individuals' values, identities, and ideological orientations. As moderator variables were not randomly assigned, all moderation analyses are exploratory and should be interpreted descriptively.

4. Discussion and implications

This study examined the impact of a large-scale carbon food label implemented in real-world grocery stores using a combination of randomized survey and field experiments. Overall, our findings partly confirm our pre-registered hypotheses (Fesenfeld & Maier, 2022). Specifically, providing information to increase awareness of the carbon label led to small but statistically significant positive effects on attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and purchase intentions. In the field experiment, the information treatment also affected revealed purchasing behavior, although effects were modest and heterogeneous across food categories. Rather than inducing broad shifts across food categories, such as a general shift towards more plant-based foods, the label primarily influenced product choice within categories. In particular, we observe increases in the average climate rating of purchased meat products, a higher overall share of Mcheck-labeled products purchased, and compositional shifts within meat consumption (e.g., away from beef toward pork and toward labeled convenience products). Taken together, these results indicate that carbon food labels can shape consumer decision-making at the margin by increasing label salience and guiding within-category substitutions, but that their capacity to substantially alter habitual food consumption patterns in stimulus-intensive retail environments remains limited.

These field-experimental findings extend previous survey-based and experimental research on carbon food labels (Camilleri et al., 2019; Faccioli et al., 2022; Meyerding et al., 2019; Rondoni & Grasso, 2021). While earlier studies often report positive effects on issue awareness, intentions, hypothetical choices, or consumption behavior in cafeteria settings, our results suggest that, when labels are embedded in everyday supermarket settings, their behavioral impact is considerably constrained. Supermarkets represent highly stimulus-intensive decision environments, characterized by high information density, multiple competing labels, price promotions, and strong habitual purchasing patterns. In such contexts, the standard placement of a carbon label on product packaging appears insufficient to trigger large cross-category substitutions, such as shifts towards more plant-based products. Instead, behavioral responses tend to occur where labels are most salient and easiest to integrate into existing habits, namely within familiar product categories.

Importantly, the increase in label awareness induced by the survey-based information treatment likely overstates what can be expected under routine retail conditions, where consumers are rarely exposed to explicit explanations of newly introduced labels. This highlights the central role of label awareness as a precondition for effectiveness. While the information intervention in our study functioned as an awareness-enhancing stimulus, real-world exposure to labels without accompanying communication is likely to generate even smaller effects. These findings underscore the importance of complementary, targeted information and advertising campaigns within the shopping context to increase label salience at the point of purchase (Kaczorowska et al., 2019; Lemken et al., 2021; Majer et al., 2022). At the same time, the observed increases in purchases of certain labeled convenience products demonstrate that information-based interventions can translate into measurable changes in revealed behavior, consistent with prior evidence that information can affect real-world choices, albeit modestly (Barabas & Jerit, 2010; Carnes & Henderson, 2025). Overall, these results point to small to moderate effects of carbon food labels and emphasize the need to embed them within broader demand-side

policy packages to achieve more substantial and durable changes in consumption patterns.

We find little evidence that the effectiveness of the carbon food label varies meaningfully over time but we find some difference in treatment effects across consumer subgroups. While treatment effects do not differ substantially between heavy and light meat consumers, nor between individuals with higher versus lower prior familiarity with the Mcheck label, men and more right-wing individuals show a modest behavioral backlash to the information treatment. On the other hand, people with higher education levels and that place larger importance on sustainability in food purchase, react more positively to the treatment. This is an important insight as backlash seems to be driven less by prior consumption habits (e.g., meat consumption levels), but treatment effects vary rather by individuals' prior attitudes, identities and ideational stances. This is in line with the broader literature on the polarization and symbolic politicization of climate change mitigation and policy (Boterman & Hartevelde, 2026; Feldman & Hart, 2018; Huber et al., 2020; Montfort, 2023; Stadelmann-Steffen & Eder, 2021).

Moreover, while the direct behavioral effects observed here are modest, carbon labels may still play a role in shaping public awareness, attitudes, and social norms over time (Judge et al., 2024; Maier, 2024). From a policy perspective, their greatest potential therefore lies not as stand-alone instruments, but as components of broader policy mixes that combine informational tools with complementary interventions, such as behavioral choice architecture measures (Bauer et al., 2022; Bauer & Reisch, 2019; Meier et al., 2022) or economic instruments including VAT reductions for low-emission foods and food-related levies (Funke et al., 2022; Klenert et al., 2023).

Several features of the Mcheck label and its implementation likely constrained its behavioral impact. First, the average climate rating of labeled products was relatively high, with many products receiving four or five stars, which may have generated ceiling effects and limited scope for differentiation. Second, labeling coverage was incomplete: at the time of the study, only about 25% of Migros food products carried the label, and unpackaged fresh fruit and vegetables, among the lowest-emission food categories, were excluded entirely. Third, labeled products were unevenly distributed across categories, with poultry products being substantially more likely to carry a label than pork or beef, potentially contributing to observed substitution patterns within meat consumption. Together, these factors suggest that both the scope and balance of label coverage matter for behavioral outcomes and warrant further experimental investigation.

From a methodological perspective, the simultaneous roll-out of the Mcheck label across all Migros stores precluded causal identification of the roll-out itself. However, because the information treatment was fully randomized and the roll-out affected treatment and control groups equally, the internal validity of our estimates is not compromised. Manipulation checks confirm that the treatment successfully increased both label awareness and the intention to consider the label when shopping. Moreover, the absence of strong interaction effects with prior label awareness suggests that the treatment primarily operated by increasing label salience rather than by selectively affecting already informed consumers. Future studies could exploit staggered roll-outs across stores or products to disentangle roll-out effects from information effects more directly.

Finally, our findings align with broader evidence on label design and visibility. The Mcheck label was not particularly prominent on product packaging and was not actively promoted within stores, potentially reducing its salience in a stimulus-intensive choice environment (Kanay et al., 2021; Kramer & Sucky, 2021; Lemken et al., 2021). The Mcheck label was not prominently displayed on all product packages, potentially reducing its impact in the stimulus-rich environment of grocery stores with a high number of choice options available. Limited label visibility may also reduce incentives for food producers to pursue emission reductions in their supply chains. While the Mcheck label received some media coverage, it was not actively advertised within the stores, reducing its effectiveness in attracting consumer attention in this stimulus-rich context. In addition, its design does not fully reflect best-practice recommendations emphasizing highly salient, intuitive formats such as traffic-light system (Lemken et al., 2021; Meyerding et al., 2019; Panzone et al., 2020; Potter et al., 2024; Rondoni & Grasso, 2021; Taufique et al., 2022). Prior research suggests that labels enabling clear within-category comparisons may be more effective in supermarket settings than those encouraging across-category comparisons (Suchier et al., 2023), a pattern consistent with our empirical results.

This study makes a novel contribution by providing one of the first large-scale, pre-registered randomized field experiments on carbon food labels in a real-world retail setting with a representative sample of consumers. Compared to prior research conducted in surveys, living labs, or food-away-from-home contexts (Brunner et al., 2018; Camilleri et al., 2019; Casati et al., 2023; Lohmann et al., 2022; Meyerding et al., 2019; Panzone et al., 2024; Rondoni & Grasso, 2021), our findings offer a realistic assessment of label effectiveness under everyday shopping conditions. At the same time, limitations remain. The study focuses on a single retailer and does not experimentally vary label design, placement, or coverage. Future research should replicate and extend these findings across different retailers, countries, and labeling schemes, and systematically test interactions

between carbon labels and other policy instruments, including choice architecture interventions and food pricing policies.

Overall, our pre-registered evidence suggests that carbon food labels alone are unlikely to bridge the intention–behavior gap in supermarket shopping. While they can meaningfully increase awareness and intentions and modestly steer choices within product categories, expectations regarding their effectiveness as a stand-alone climate policy tool should remain cautious. Demand-side interventions remain essential for reducing food-related emissions, but their success will depend on combining informational measures with stronger structural and economic policies capable of reshaping food environments and consumption patterns at scale.

Funding sources

Funding: This work was supported by the Swiss Network for International Studies (SNIS) – (grant number: C21073)

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study and relevant study documentation will be available upon publication in the Harvard Dataverse public repository.

Code availability statement

The R code used to analyze the datasets during the current study will be available upon publication in the Harvard Dataverse public repository.

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